

Site: SPHINX Season GS 80

RUMP PASSAGE

22/IX/80

Area: NW-Fc1 ^{CHAMBER} Square 1 Locus Number 1

Progress of Excavation 22/IX/80: After cleaning floor area to have a clean zone for dumping, we cleared chamber 1 - niche like space at top of upward part of passage. There was about 1 cubic meter of loose clean sand w/ carbon pieces, a few limestone chips. No sign of modern inclusions. This clearing shows the bedrock end (E) of the niche slopes down into its "floor" to the edge drop off to chamber 2 below. Here, at the threshold, several stones noted previously - one cut to straight sides, look to be purposely set across the threshold. There were many mid sized limestone chips and fragments packed in where Locus Description these meet the slope of the floor (bedrock) The fill taken out is being sifted to salvage the carbon pieces.

Are the stone pieces across the threshold remains of Phase I packing thus indicating the feature is earlier? Or are they remains of blocking

Location in Square the whole or entrance, to the niche shortly after it was cut after Phase I already extant? Is the sand fallen out of packing from Phase I masonry before or after Barozee excavation? Or was

Under Locus _____ Over Locus it (the niche) purposely filled

Locus Dimensions with sand?

Levels _____

Analysis of non-artifactual materials _____